

With increasing concentration of the ligand, $-E_{1/2}^0$ values are shifted to more negative side in the case of Zn(II), Pd(II) and Cu(II) indicating complex formation, while in the case of Co(II) and Ni(II), $-E_{1/2}^0$ values are shifted markedly towards more positive values, but again shifts to more negative values successively, as the concentration of the ligand is increased upto $M:L=1:4$. This positive shift⁶ may be considered as due to their easier reduction to the amalgam than to the solid metal.

The values of αn are obtained from the slope of the plots of $-E_{a.e.}$ vs $[\log i/(i_a-i)]$ in the case of Pd(II) and Cu(II) complexes with PBT or $-E_{a.e.}$ vs $[\log i/(i_a-i) - 0.546 \log t]$ in the case of Zn(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes with PBT. The plots are straight lines and the slope is equal to $-0.0542/\alpha n$. However, the slope values obtained do not agree with the theoretical values⁶ which also suggest that the metals as well as their complexes with PBT reduce irreversibly at d.m.e. The intercept of the same plot gave the value of $-E_{1/2}^0$, which was used to calculate $K_{f,n}^0$ after evaluating the values of $D_0^{1/2}$ by using Ilkovic equation $D_0^{1/2} = [(i_a/607) n \text{ cm}^{3/2} t^{1/2}]$. It is evident that the values of αn and $K_{f,n}^0$ are related to $-E_{1/2}^0$ as well as ligand concentration. The values of αn evaluated are somewhat larger than the usual because the variation of $-E_{1/2}^0$ was found smaller than the usual.

References

1. C. L. JAIN, B. L. KHANDRIWAL, and P. N. MUNDLEY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 1769.
2. J. HEVROVSKY and N. R. ZUMAN, "Practical Polarography", Academic Press, N. Y., 1963, pp. 179, 397, 609.
3. J. J. LINGANE, "Electroanalytical Chemistry", Interscience, N. Y., 1958, p. 258.
4. Y. AYABE and H. MATSUDA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1955, **28**, 428.
5. Y. ISRAEL and L. MEITES, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1964, **8**, 99.
6. J. J. LINGANE and B. A. LOVERIDGE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 438.

Formation of U(VI) and Th(IV) Complexes with Chromotropic Acid in Solution

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MEHROTRA¹ *et al* and other workers^{2,3} have studied the coordination compounds of chromotropic acid (CTA). This acid provides two hydroxyl groups for coordination and hence it is interesting to study the complex formation. The systems $UO_2(II)$ -CTA and $Th(IV)$ -CTA have not been studied so far. We have therefore undertaken the study of these two systems in this investigation.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR quality. The disodium salt of CTA (Loba Chemie) was of G.R. grade. Elico pH-meter model LI-15 with glass-SCE assembly was used to determine the hydrogen ion concentration of the reaction mixture. Conductance measurements were made on a Systronics direct reading conductivity bridge (model-303) with a cell having a cell constant 1 cm^{-1} .

The following mixtures were subjected to pH-metric and conductometric titrations against standard alkali.

1. 25 ml ligand solution ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) + 25 ml conductivity water.
2. 25 ml ligand solution ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) + 25 ml metal solution ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$).
3. 25 ml ligand solution ($2 \times 10^{-3} M$) + 25 ml metal solution ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$).

The titrations were performed in duplicate to test for reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

The appearance of inflection and breaks in the ligand titration curve indicates that one mole of ligand is utilised by one mole of alkali which corresponds to the neutralization of one of the phenolic -OH groups of CTA. The inflection and break for the second -OH group could not be observed due to the formation of intramolecular hydrogen bond. Such observations were made by Dodwad *et al*⁴ in their study on proton-ligand stability constant and by the present authors⁵ in their study on uranyl complexes of Schiff bases.

The reaction may be represented as

In the second set of titration where the ligand is mixed with metal ion viz., $UO_2(II)$ and $Th(IV)$, there is a decrease in the pH of the solution. This is indicative of formation of the complex. The curves corresponding to metal-ion titration shows two inflections.

The first inflection corresponds to the neutralisation of possibly $H[M(NO_3)_2OH]$ $\{M=UO_2(II)$ or $Th(IV)\}$, the form in which $M(NO_3)_2$ exists in aqueous solution. It is in accordance with the existence of $H[AuCl_2OH]$; as suggested by Kharasch *et al*⁶. The second inflection corresponds to the formation of complex ion, $[MA(NO_3)_2]^{2-}$, which has been in accordance with the structures reported by the authors^{5,7}.

Fig. 1. pH-metric and conductometric titration curves of CTA in absence and presence of Th(IV) and U(VI) with 0.1 M NaOH—Curves 1 & 1'—(1×10^{-3} M) CTA; Curves 2 & 2'—(1×10^{-3} M) CTA + (1×10^{-3} M) Th(IV); Curves 3 & 3'—(2×10^{-3} M) CTA + (1×10^{-3} M) Th(IV); Curves 4 & 4'—(1×10^{-3} M) CTA + (1×10^{-3} M) UO_2^{2+} ; Curves 5 & 5'—(2×10^{-3} M) CTA + (1×10^{-3} M) UO_2^{2+} .

The third set of titration also shows only two inflections as in the case of second set of titration suggesting that there is no possibility of 3 : 1 complexes. The reaction taking place in the whole process of titration may be represented as follows :

Set II :

Set III :

The formation of the complexes as discussed above have been verified by conductometric titrations. The observed plots (Fig. 1) confirm the formation of complexes as shown by equations given above.

References

1. C. K. SHARMA, V. D. GUPTA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **50**, 207.
2. R. WAKE, H. MIYATA and TOBIK, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1968, **41**, 1952.
3. A. BANERJEE and A. K. DEY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 995.
4. S. S. DODWAD, M. G. DATAR and I. R. PATIL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **22A**, 89.
5. P. S. PRABHU and S. S. DODWAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 546.
6. M. S. KHARASCH and H. S. INBELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **53**, 2702.
7. P. S. PRABHU and S. S. DODWAD, Proceedings of Symposium on Fundamental and Applied Electrochemistry, March 1982, p. 87.

Effect of Acetic Acid on the Oxidation of Mandelic Acid by Manganese(III) Pyrophosphate

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OXIDATION of mandelic acid (MA) has been investigated by different workers using several oxidizing agents. The kinetics of oxidation of MA by cerium(IV)¹⁻³, vanadium(V)⁴⁻⁶, manganese(III)⁷, peroxydisulphate⁸ and bromine⁹ has been studied in aqueous acidic media, and by chromic acid¹⁰⁻¹³ both in aqueous acidic media and in acetic acid-water binary mixtures. However, no data seems to have been reported on the kinetics of oxidation of MA by manganese(III) pyrophosphate. Manganese(III) pyrophosphate is a good selective one electron oxidant towards organic compounds. It has been widely used by Waters and coworkers¹⁴ to study the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of a variety of organic substrates. The investigations of Waters and coworkers were carried out in aqueous acidic medium, but as many organic compounds are insoluble in water their oxidation kinetics cannot be investigated in aqueous medium. One has to use other solvents like acetic acid, dioxane, acetonitrile, etc. Bakore and Narain¹⁵ had reported rate enhancement due to acetic acid in the oxidation of MA by chromic acid while our preliminary experiment showed retardation in the rate of oxidation due to the presence of acetic acid in reaction mixture for the oxidation of MA by manganese pyrophosphate. It was therefore, thought worthwhile to investigate in detail the oxidation of mandelic acid by manganese(III) pyrophosphate in

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